

The Tradition of Cinema and the Tradition in Cinema - A Cultural analysis based on the history of Malayalam Cinema

Santhosh H.K

ABSTRACT

This essay seeks to analyze the evolution of Malayalam cinema by linking it with the evolution of Malayalee social identity. Here we examine how a narrative tradition that reaffirms traditional feudal values has evolved in cinema and is rooted in a caste-centric and patriarchal ideology.

Keyword: Film studies, Malayali Visual Culture, Tradition, Identity.

One of the Namboodiri jokes calls cinema as a thief. Even after decades of evolvement thoughts on cinema still gropes around in darkness. Cinema exists now more or less outside of it. In the beginning, cinema's lives outside the theatre were treated as its afterlife. But cinema's sojourn on TV, radio, internet and home cinema has transformed the whole scenario.

Even as theatres were closed down cinema opened new doors for its existence. Most of Malayalam cinemas do not get exposure in theatres. However, they continue to breathe variously and in fragmented ways. It has lost its textual homogeneity owing to its migration to different media. They survive as fragments of bits of humor, punch dialogues and so on. They are subjected to mixing, reinterpretation and remake and find place in stage shows, political satire and even in public meetings of all sorts. What a student and critic of cinema should recognize is that these are not afterlives of cinema but its exterior lives. It has to be recognized as a multi-screen presence before gauging its influence on society and suggesting measures to reform it.

The unique trajectory of the recent controversy triggered by the attack of an actress by thugs from the world of cinema calls for close attention. The initial response from within the cinema world was a sanitization effort by claiming the attackers to be a criminal community which had nothing to do with the sacred precincts of cinema. They had to content with the retort that the anti-women turn of society is the creation of anti-women cinema.

Prithviraj was applauded for vowing to keep away from anti-women cinema, while Renjith was denigrated for anti-women elements in his cinema. In fact, Malayalam cinema has to be examined from the premise of the formation of our sensibility and the history of the development of the Kerala society and the cultural logics generated by it. Therefore, a close analysis of cinema as tradition and tradition in cinema becomes imperative. The social consciousness supposed to be generated by cinema has, in fact, evolved in our cultural tradition, which, in turn, remains as the consciousness of tradition in cinema.

A clear distinction has not generally been made among culture, tradition, and identity. **Lauri Honko** identifies tradition as the cultural elements a community projects in different times and contexts. Only a part of them come to the fore at a particular moment. It is the source or energy of culture. It is a temporal phenomenon that creates a culture and its boundaries get redefined all the time.

“The important aspect of “tradition” defined as the stuff out of which cultures are made is that it need not be described as a functioning system.

Rather, it is a cumulative entity. Its boundaries will change with every new person entering the group or passing away. Tradition, in other words, would denote the cultural potential or resource, not the actual culture of the group.” (Honko)

The term culture also has been interpreted in different ways. Though the term represents a mass, the amalgamation of varying elements gives it the form of a functional system. The idea of culture stresses the performative side rather than its contents. It can only be discovered in the perspectives, thoughts and practice of it. To Honko it is an umbrella term and tradition is something specific within it.

The transformation of tradition into culture entails a process of organization. It involves acceptance, rejection, deferment, integration and so on. A step ahead along this line takes us to the province of identity. The systematization

of tradition becomes more focused and precise in the case of identity. Elements like language, region, music, dance, attire, architecture, history, anthropology, ritual, etc. will play a part in it. They function as symbols or icons of the mass.

He summarizes these ideas in the form of a chart below.

The Malayali identity represented by Malayalam Cinema is to be examined considering cinema as a cultural form. One has to seek the roots of the feudal, caste, anti-Dalit, anti-women, apolitical attitudes alleged to be nurtured by mainstream Malayalam cinema beyond cinema. They are termed mainstream cinema not merely because they tread the path between art and commerce, but because they are the cinema of the bourgeois formed and acquired political dominance in Kerala.

‘Neelakkuyil’ produced in 1954 is characterized as the first Malayalam film that exhibited Kerala life style. It has succeeded in representing the plurality of Kerala society despite having its base on middle class life. ‘Chemmeen’ attempted to give voice to the marginalized fishing community. ‘Nirmalyam’ (1973) stands out by carving out a different cultural premise. It inaugurated the tradition of treating Muslim identity and Muslim community in general as the ‘other’. Even as Renjith, Shaji Kailas cinemas are denigrated for their feudal, monarchist contents, sufficient attention has not been given to the direction Malayalam fiction, especially novel took after the eighties.

Even writers who began with exploring the existential anxieties of the rootless modern man shifted their attention to the vastness of tradition and pedigree. M.T’s film released in should be the first Malayalam film where an unequivocal anti-Dalit and anti-reservationist sentiment is made. Toeing this line, Priyadarsan’s ‘Aryan’ (1988) establishes the political clout of Brahminic priesthood over class struggle. It almost coincided with the anti-reservationist agitation triggered by the implementation of the Mandal commission report in 1990.

With the advent of television in the field of visual media, cinema faced a serious challenge in the eighties and Nineties. Arguably the Prudential World Cup in 1983 and the assassination of Indira Gandhi the following year were watersheds in the history of television. To own a television set became a new status symbol. In the 1990s, with the advent of cable networks, our living rooms were literally flooded with news and music. Channels vied with each other to bring in the latest and the intriguing. And often they infringed upon traditional media ethics.

The higher penetration rate has heavily impacted on our social habits and outlooks too. Evenings are for soap operas or reality shows. Women huddle in front of the glimmering screen, invariably their eyes riveted to it, ready to weep for the pangs of characters. By the half of last decade, private channels had almost replaced the staid state owned television and redefined our visual sensibility. An average Malayalee knows the world through television. What he sees on it true. In other words, the infallibility once attributed to print media has become the privilege of television. The factoid ‘camera does not lie’ is the plank on which the faith rests. Never ever have our channels dithered in taking advantage of this trust.

In the early 1990s Asianet, the first private player in Kerala, televised a documentary on the ruthless and unhygienic slaughtering of cattle in an abattoir in Trivandrum with the warning 'carrying women and the weak-minded are advised to abstain from watching.' In hindsight the gory scenes that splashed the screen and the minds seem to have been the curtain raiser of many a visual extravaganza to follow. Later Asianet and archrival Surya set new standards by repeatedly telecasting the visuals of a nut whacking a government employ to death.

By depicting an upper caste popular hero establishing his manliness by raping the identity of a dark skinned lower class woman, Padmarajan gave an anticipatory cultural justification to the upper caste rapes of Dalit women in North India in 'Karyilakkattupole'. Both of these screen writers who had formulated the family film format during the eighties paved the way for film makers like Renjith and Priyadrasan in the nineties.

In order to counter this dominance of television, Malayalam cinema has turned to superstar cinema, which is steeped in violence, misogyny, Brahminical ideology and feudal values.

Feudalism happens to be modern Malayali's nostalgic reminiscence of a past thriving on caste, patriarchy, collective families and so on. This nostalgia inspired the transformation from iconoclastic heroes to heroes who recover the iconic structures of the past. Padmarajan's 'Thinkalazhcha Nalla Divasam' (1985) is among the early films that take the Malayali film viewer to the reestablishment of collective traditional families. So does the later Sathyan Anthikkad film Kudumbapuranam. It was a definite departure from the trend of depicting individual struggles and anonymous urban life until the middle of the eighties as witnessed in I.V. Sasi films.

Films of this period attempt to glorify the virtues of collective families. In their context a marriage is not an affair between two individuals, but a social relationship occurring within a vast collective family. They are quick to reject and denigrate the present day redefinition of man woman relationship in the like of living together. In short, the roots have to be sought further back than the mere surface of popular cinema.

In fact, the bourgeois of Kerala evolved into a new religion from its social and economic empowerment aided by expatriate income, the growth of bureaucracy, and quasi-urbanization. Emulating the upper caste became an indicator of social mobility with the institutionalization of the family. Pre-renaissance practices such as rituals, superstitious rites return with a vengeance. The social attitudes the middle class appropriated such as contempt for manual labor and the labor class, anti-Dalitism, moral vigilantism, machismo, disrespect to women permeated to cinema as well.

The transmigration of our cinema from class-politics to apoliticism occurred almost simultaneously. Despite their weak, childish, and sentimental execution, it cannot be denied that the films of the seventies dealt with marginalized lives and varying forms of class-politics. With the arrival of the like of M. T and Sathyan Anthikkad cinema was transplanted from the premise of streets and work places to that of sagas of the f

The period marked the transformation from sexual freedom to stringent morality. The eighties witnessed the emergence of various movements to reform religion. The result was the construction of bigger and more opulent temples, churches, and mosques. Nocturnal religious preaching began to focus on how to become a good husband or a good wife as well as on what would be a good religious life. The new found morality funded by the neo-rich manifested in the form of vigilantism always in the look out for morally abhorrent or deviant behavior and itching to correct them by force and violence.

Interestingly, an interlude of soft porn cinema followed provoking various kinds of responses before the onset of cinemas celebrating the family. In Shaji Kailas, Renjith cinemas the tradition of including scenes of sexual promiscuity at the expense of sub-heroines reappear in different guises. They are achieved with the help of voyeuristic camera angles and the celebration of masculine sexual exploits in the form of dialogues with ill-concealed sexual innuendoes. (Paper presented in the concluding session at the National seminar on 'Tradition in Cinema - Tradition of Cinema' at University of Calicut conducted by the Folklore Department on March 8, 2017.)

REFERENCES

- [1] Honko , "The Folklore Process." *Folklore Fellows' Summer School Programme, Turku*, 1991:25-47.
- [2] Honko, "Epic and Identity:National, Regional, Communal, Individual", *Oral Tradition*, 11/1, 1996: 18-36
- [3] Koven, Mikel J. "Folklore Studies and Popular Film and Television: A Necessary Critical Survey." *The Journal of American Folklore*, vol. 116, no. 460, University of Illinois Press, 2003, pp. 176-95.
- [4] Williams, Raymond, and Dana Polan. "Film and the Cultural Tradition." *Cinema Journal*, vol. 52, no. 3, [University of Texas Press, Society for Cinema & Media Studies], 2013, pp. 19-24.